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The Impact of AI-Enhanced Automation and Efficiency on Project Success: Does Ease of Use Matter?

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ABSTRACT

Based on the Technology Acceptance Model, this study examines AI automation, efficiency and the impact of ease of use in AI tool adoption and integration, which in turn enhance project success. The study adopted a quantitative survey-based methodology from a sample of 200 respondents from different construction sectors in Islamabad. The result showed that AI automation (AIA) and AI efficiency (AIE) have a positive impact on project success. The results also showed that ease of use positively moderates the impact of AI automation and AI efficiency on project success. The study holds implications for how leaders and managers can leverage AI automation and efficiency for improved chances of project success, and to enhance users' ease of use to maximize AI's potential for better project results within medium to large-sized construction projects.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence Automation, Artificial Intelligence Efficiency, Ease of use, Project Success.

Introduction

A project is successful when project objectives are gained within the given scopes of time, budget, and quality standards (Bannerman, 2008). When a project achieves its goals and objectives, it creates a positive impact toward project success (Rohman, et al. 2017). Construction projects in developing countries face tight budgets and timelines, coupled with traditional project management methods (Othman, & Ahmed, 2013). These projects also face other challenges of high labor costs, environmental regulations, and market competition (Felipe, & Kumar, 2014). This affects speed of project delivery as well as its efficiency (Ofori, 2007). These challenges require more modern tools and systems like AI automation and AI-enhanced efficiency. Accordingly, this paper explores if and how AI automation and AI -enhanced efficiency contribute to project success in construction projects in a developing country. Additionally, it explores if the AI tools' ease of use contributes to enhanced project success.

As developing countries face challenges of economic stability, technological advancement, and good governance- factors that play a critical role in project success (Rezvani, & Khosravi, 2018), there is a greater need for construction projects in these countries to adopt AI tools. Adoption of AI in construction projects is likely to help make these systems efficient, modify new techniques, and support decision-making, increasing chances of project success (Nam, et al. 2021). Owing to the rapid growth of technology (Jessen, 2011). The use of artificial intelligence project management tools is increasing, which enhances automation of planning, resource allocation, decision-making, risk assessment, and scheduling (Linda, et al. 2025; Sljivic, et al. 2015). These tools include Microsoft Project, which automates scheduling and tasks management, and maximizes resource allocation (Celestin, & Vanitha, 2017). Primavera is an AI-based risk assessment tool that identifies potential issues before they are critical (Li, et al. 2024). Team communication is facilitated by Trello platforms (Joiner, 2023). JIRA with AI used to monitor issues and enhance software quality assurance (Keshireddy, 2023).

This By automating repetitive tasks such as scheduling, budgeting, risk management, and

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resource allocation, artificial intelligence (AI) provides opportunities to revolutionize project management (Shoushtari, et al. 2024). In comparison to manual scheduling, artificial intelligence (AI) can automate both simple and complex resource allocation and decision-making processes, leading to improved time management and ensuring higher accuracy (Akeiber, 2025). AI-powered automation tools including scheduling software and resource planners, help project managers and enable them to better decision making and more strategic (Pal, et al. 2023). AI automation reduces human error, resulting in better resource allocation and AI systems can dynamically vary resource allocation in real-time (Ramamoorthi, 2021). AI automation is transforming the construction sector by reducing costs and making the operations flexible (Zaland, et al. 2024). AI automation minimizes human intervention and enhances several processes such as material management, monitoring, assessment and sites supervision (Onukwulu, et al. 2024). Accordingly, this study aims to explore the impact of AI automation on project success.

AI efficiency improves inter-project team collaboration and communication management (Keshireddy, 2023). AI efficiency enhances project success through improving decision-making, optimizing performance, and reducing waste of resources and time (Shamim, 2024). AI efficiency in stakeholder management improves engagement and transparency, which enhances decision-making and enhances stakeholder satisfaction (Hasan, 2024). Studies report that use of artificial intelligence (AI) reduces risks, improves the perceived fairness of within organizations (Ali et al., 2025), and also enhance project efficiency and success rate (Salimimoghadam, et al. 2025). Others also report that user-friendly AI systems, and AI ease of use contribute to better project outcomes (Alevizos, et al. 2023). Ease of use of AI systems enable project teams to interact smoothly with technology, leading to improved decision-making and enhanced project success (Reznikov, 2025). Studies also highlights that ease of use in AI not only affects project success but also maintain sustainability in project environments by ensuring continuous AI adoption, (Shang et al. 2023) These findings suggest that AI's ease of use plays an important role in determining its impact on project success, particularly in enhancing efficiency, decision-making, and overall project success (Waqar, et al. 2023).

The acceptance of new technologies has become a critical field of interest in this era of rapid technological advancements. Understanding how users accept and adopt new technology is essential as various facets of life. To make it easier theoretical models are crucial for understanding user acceptance. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is one. The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al. 2024). UTAUT is a predominant model extensively employed in understanding technology adoption in the education context (Granic, 2022). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), is a widely used framework that explains how users come to accept and use a new technology and the adoption of AI are driven by two factors: Perceived Usefulness (PU), or the belief that AI improves project outcomes, and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), which reflects how easy the technology is to learn and apply (Davis, 1989). TAM suggests that users' perceptions of ease of use shape their willingness to adopt AI tools, which in turn enhance project success. While automation

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and efficiency improve performance, their true impact depends on how comfortably team members can interact with AI systems (Rogers, 1962). Advanced AI technology may fail to enhance project success if users find it complex. Hence, ease of use strengthens the link between AI-enabled automation and project efficiency by fostering user acceptance, trust, and sustained utilization

The key contributions of this study lie in its exploration of how artificial intelligence (AI) can streamline project workflows, reduce human error, and enhance overall efficiency. This study reports that investments in AI technologies alone are insufficient, and suggests that in order to adopt AI technologies, project managers should prioritize user-friendly AI systems to improve efficiency and overall project success.

2. Literature Review

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which introduced by Fred Davis, emphasizes how users come to accept and use new technologies. This model proposed two key factors that influence technology adoption. Perceived Usefulness (PU), or the belief that AI improves project outcomes, and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), which reflects how easy technology is to learn and apply (Davis, 1989). TAM suggests that users' perceptions of usefulness and ease of use shape their willingness to adopt AI tools, which in turn enhance project success. While automation and efficiency improve performance, their true impact depends on how comfortably team members can interact with AI systems. Advanced AI technology may fail to enhance project success if users find it complex. Hence, ease of use strengthens the link between AI-enabled automation and project efficiency by fostering user acceptance, trust, and sustained utilization

Artificial Intelligence Automation on Project Success

AI automation has a significant impact on project success, which helps to form the structure of projects, their execution, and success (Hashfi, & Raharjo, 2023). AI automation has a capacity to increase decision-making process, reduce repetitive tasks, and maximize resource allocation that increase productivity and efficiency in project (Adepoju, 2025). Artificial Intelligence (AI) help in real time challenges and automate task on time which help in resource allocation (Musliner, et al. 2002). Artificial Intelligence helps in improving the results of projects through higher efficiency and automation (Hossain, et al. 2024). AI tools help the project manager to examine actual-time data and capacity to take right decision at right time which enhances the quality of decision-making and prevents disruption in the delivery of projects (Mahmood, et al. 2023). Project success rate increase where AI is utilized within project management procedures, AI automation increases the entire project delivery time, cost-effectiveness, and quality standard (Obiuto, et al. 2024). Study indicates that AI automation like predictive analytics and machine learning can introduce improved risk management and forecasting accuracy that enhances the success rate of projects (Diameh, et al. 2025). Study also shows that AI is transforming conventional approaches to project success and providing an opportunity for innovation and creativity in complex field of projects (Salimimoghadam, et al. 2025).

H1. Artificial Intelligence Automation has a positive impact on project success.

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Artificial Intelligence Efficiency on Project Success

Artificial Intelligence has been used to promote the success of projects, mainly due to its impact on effectiveness and decision-making processes (Wamba-Taguimdje, et al. 2020). AI is used to drive the automation of repetitive work, enhance the allocation of resources, and drive data-driven decision-making (Akhtaruzzaman, et al. 2024). The use of AI in project improved project performance and increased stakeholder satisfaction (Joshi, 2024). Predictive analytics of AI can also detect possible bottlenecks, lowering risks at an early stage of the project (Nabeel, 2024). Through the real time use of AI, effectiveness of projects has been improved through the detection and rectification of problems within time (Bello, et al. 2023). AI help to track project work constantly and improve performance which increases project success rate and provide motivation to stakeholders. (Bah Esseme, et al. 2025). Project performance enhanced as AI continues to evolve and combined with technologies like blockchain and IoT (Bhumichai, et al. 2024). The ability of AI to enhance decision-making, process automation, and resource allocation all this create impact on project success (Nasr, & Asharee, 2024).

H2. Artificial Intelligence Efficiency has a positive impact on project success.

Impact of Ease of Use on AI Automation and Project Success

The ease of use of AI has become popular on its contribution to project success, this study highlights how easier-to-use AI systems contribute to improved project performance (Almalki, 2025). The ease of use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) significantly influences both AI automation effectiveness and overall project success. When AI systems are user-friendly, they lower the technical barriers for adoption, allowing a broader range of stakeholders to engage with and leverage AI tools (Wamba-Taguimdje, et al. 2020). Project teams can easily communicate with AI systems if they are easier to use, AI ease of use contributing to improved decision-making and project performance (Bah Esseme, et al. 2025). Study shows that if AI tools are user-friendly, adoption had been less difficult and project implementation be more effective (Chen, et al. 2024). Artificial intelligence systems through ease of use, support project managers in making good decisions and the success of the project do not need much technical expertise (Williams, 2024). AI technologies with ease-of-use help in resources allocation with minimal effort, reduce risk, and boost project efficiency while aligning with the knowledge and skills of project teams (Pashazanous, 2025). AI enabled scheduling applications with a minimum approach and ease of use enable project teams to outsource the repetitive tasks to automation. This approach helps to saves time for the teams and enables them to focus on further tasks that make projects successful (Singh, 2024). Ease of use of AI is important in establishing how it influences project success, it helps in increasing productivity, judgment, and overall project success (Tominc, et al. 2023).

H3. AI Ease of Use Moderate the impact of Artificial Intelligence Automation on project success.

Impact of Ease of use on AI Efficiency and Project Success

The ease of use of Artificial Intelligence systems plays a crucial role in enhancing efficiency and overall project success (Hossain, et al. 2024). Studies based on Technology Acceptance Model suggest that perceived ease of use significantly influences user acceptance and engagement with AI technologies (Na, et al. 2022). When AI tools are easy and user-friendly, they reduce cognitive effort, minimize training requirements, and allow users of varying technical backgrounds to integrate AI more effectively into their workflows (Ghorbani, 2023). This increased accessibility leads to faster adoption, smoother automation, and greater operational efficiency key factors that directly impact project performance (Ghorbani, 2023). user-friendly AI fosters greater collaboration and trust among stakeholders, aligning AI capabilities more closely with project objectives and ease of use of AI not only promote efficiency in automation but also acts as a strategic enabler of project success by promoting adoption, effectiveness, and sustainable innovation (Campos, & Shakhovska, 2025).

H4. AI Ease of Use Moderate the impact of Artificial Intelligence Efficiency on project success.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Methodology

Participants and Procedure

The study adopted a survey-based quantitative approach. Data were collected from employees of construction organizations in Islamabad through online questionnaires. The links to the online questionnaires were distributed to 250 employees through mutual contacts. Respondents were assured of anonymity and confidentiality of their responses. Initially, 230 responses were received, which were then reviewed for pattern responses. 30 responses were removed due to pattern or blank responses, and the final sample included 200 responses.

Measures

The study adopted previously validated scales. The questionnaires were designed in English, as it is the medium of instruction and official communication in Pakistani organizations, and is well understood by people. Each scale adopted a 5-point Likert scale unless otherwise indicated, where the responses meant 1= Strongly disagree, to 5=

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Strongly Agree.

Artificial Intelligence Automation was measured using the sub-scales of Abu-Khaled (2020). AI automation was measured using the 5-items and the scale alpha reliability was .951. To measure Artificial Intelligence efficiency, we used the 5-item scale developed by Abu-Khaled (2020). The scale alpha reliability was .910. To measure Ease of Use, we used 5 items scale developed by Abu-Khaled (2020). The scale alpha reliability was .879. Project success was measured using the sub-scales of (Salman, 2018). Project success was measured using the 14-items and the scale alpha reliability was .704. The measures used in the study are summarized below, in table 1.

Table 1: Measures

Variable	Variable Type	Scale Number of items	Scale Source
AI-Automation	Independent variable	5	Abu-Khaled (2020)
AI-Efficiency	Independent Variable	5	Abu-Khaled (2020)
Ease of Use	Moderating Variable	5	Abu-Khaled (2020)
Project Success	Dependent Variable	14	(Shan, 2018)

Results

Table 2 shows demographic details of the study respondents. Out of 200 respondents of 200 respondents 17 respondents were matric which equal to 8.5% and 6 respondents were collage/diploma which equal to 3.0% and 6 respondents were bachelors which is equal to 3.0% and 100 respondents were masters which equal to 50% and last 71 respondents were above masters which equal to 35.5% and regarding experiences of 200 respondents 16 respondents had 0-3 experiences which equal to 8.0% and 5 respondents had 4-6 experiences which equal to 2.5% and 16 respondents had 7-9 experiences which equal to 8.0% and 103 respondents had 10-12 experiences which equal to 51.5 % and last 60 respondents had above 12 experiences which equal to 30.0 %.

Table 2: Demographic

		Frequency	Percent
Gander	Male	129	64.5
	Female	71	35.5
	Total	200	100.0
Ag	20-25	14	7.0
	26-30	7	3.5
	31-35	15	7.5
	36-40	86	43.0
	Above 40	78	39.0
	Total	200	100.0
Qualification	Matric	17	8.5
	Collage\Diploma	6	3.0
	Bachelor	6	3.0

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	Masters	100	50.0
	Above Masters	71	35.5
	Total	200	100.0
Experience	0-3	16	8.0
	4-6	5	2.5
	7-9	16	8.0
	10-12	103	51.5
	Above 12	60	30.0
	Total	200	100.0

Table 3 shows mean, standard deviation and correlation coefficient of study variables. The results show that AIA, AIE and EOU have a significant positive association with PS. AIA & PS ($\gamma = .685^{**}$, $p < 0.000$). AIE & PS ($\gamma = .535^*$, $p < 0.000$). EOU & PS ($\gamma = .187$, $p < 0.000$). Study shows all variables had a positive association and all variables were significant.

Table 3: Correlation, Means, Standard Deviations, and Reliability

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4
1 AIA	15.2	2.00	(951)			
2 AIE	13.1	4.14	-.019*	(910)		
3 PS	12.2	4.34	.685**	.535*	(704)	
4 EOU	23.5	4.12	-.003**	.537*	.187	(879)

Notes: n = 200 AIA= Artificial Intelligence Automation, AIE= Artificial Intelligence Efficiency, PS= Project Success, EOU= Ease of Use.

The structural model was assessed through Hayes model. The results, depicted in table 4 show that AIA has a significant positive impact on PS ($\beta = 0.66$, $p = 0.002$) thus hypothesis 1 is supported. AIE also has a significant positive impact on PS ($\beta = 0.53$, $p = 0.007$) thus hypothesis 2 is also supported. EOU positively moderates the relationship between AIA and PS ($\beta = 0.45$, $p = 0.009$) thus hypothesis 3 is also supported. Lastly, EOU moderates positively between AIE and ($\beta = 0.56$, $p = 0.025$) thus hypothesis 4 is also supported.

Table 4 Moderation Analysis

Hypothesis	Relationship	β	SE	t-value	p-value	LLCI	ULCI	Decision
H1	AIAPS	0.66	0.31	12.15	0.002	.6169	.8165	Supported
H2	AIEPS	0.53	0.25	10.18	0.007	.5343	.7350	Supported
H3	EOUAIA+PS	0.45	0.20	8.16	0.009	.5313	.6213	Supported
H4	EOUAIE+PS	0.56	0.31	10.13	0.025	.5623	.7415	Supported

Notes: * $p < 0.02$; ** $p < 0.07$; *** $p < 0.009$, * $p < 0.02$, AIA= Artificial Intelligence automation, AIE= Artificial Intelligence efficiency, EOU= Ease of use, PS= Project success

Discussion, Practical Implication and Conclusion

Discussion

This study explores the transformative role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in enhancing project success by focusing on its automation and efficiency, with the ease of use of AI tools. AI has enhanced project success by automating project tasks such as scheduling, budgeting, and risk management, allowing project managers to focus on strategic

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decision making. However, the success of AI adoption largely depends on the ease with which project teams can easily utilize AI tools. Tools that are easy lead to higher adoption rates and smoother integration into workflows, which enhances the overall effectiveness of automation and efficiency and project success.

The Previous literatures highlight how AI-driven automation and efficiency influence project success, Artificial Intelligence (AI) significantly enhances project success through automation and efficiency (Allouzi, 2024). Studies had shown that the integration of AI in project management positively influences success dimensions such as time, cost, and quality performance (Taboada, 2023). The effectiveness of AI adoption often depends on user-related factors, particularly the perceived ease of use which moderates the relationship between automation, efficiency and project success (FakhrHosseini, 2024). Technology Acceptance Model, indicates that when AI systems are perceived as easy to use, employees are more likely to adopt them, which turn to enhance success rate (Na, 2022). Previous literature also shows the importance for organizations looking to implement AI in their project management practices and user-friendly AI systems for maximizing the benefits of automation and improving overall project success (Saha, 2019).

The study used a quantitative, survey-based methodology to examine the relationships between AI automation, AI efficiency, ease of use and project success. The study adopted a cross-sectional time horizon, with data collected at a single point in time. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data and data analysis was performed through Hayes process model to assess the relationships between the variables and providing insights into how these variables influence project performance.

Practical Implication

The study offers an important implication for construction sectors organization. First, the study provides valuable insight into how AI automation and efficiency enhance project success, this helps project managers to manage repetitive tasks, scheduling, budgeting and evaluation processes. In scheduling process AI helps project managers to automate both simple and complex resources allocation and decision-making process. AI automation, efficiency reduces human biasness and increases accuracy in real time and increases flexibility during operations. This acknowledgment brings positive emotions among organization team. Therefore, project managers should prioritize to adopt AI in construction sectors to automatize daily routine process and project success. Moreover, this process improves decision making and overseeing ongoing processes.

Secondly, the study reiterates the importance of AI ease of use. AI ease of use creates an environment among team members which helps to maintain sustainability in project operations. AI through ease of use, support project managers in making good decisions and help in resources allocation with minimal effort, reduce risk, and boost project efficiency. Project managers should monitor how AI tools are easy to use for their staff. Ease of use of AI helps to increase efficiency in project and project success rate.

Future Recommendation

Along with practical contributions this study has a few limitations. First our study is based on AI automation, efficiency on project success with moderating role of ease of use and

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data was collected from various construction organizations of Rawalpindi and Islamabad. Future research may focus on specific areas such as healthcare, manufacturing, or IT which give a more comprehensive view of the interaction between AI automation, efficiency project success and ease of use. Second, we adopt quantitative methods for our study. Future studies may adopt qualitative approaches (e.g., interviews, focus groups) to study deeper insights into how AI automation and efficiency impact project success with ease of use. Third, our study focused construction sector and future research are recommended to examine how AI affects project success in various industries (e.g., healthcare, education, manufacturing, IT) to increase generalizability.

Conclusion

This study emphasizes the significant role of Artificial Intelligence automation, efficiency with ease of use in enhancing project success, particularly within the construction industry. Our Study findings show that AI automation, efficiency and ease of use have a direct, positive impact on project success. Aligning with the Technology Acceptance Model which underscores the importance of ease of use and was found to have the most substantial influence on project success, as it facilitates smoother workflows, scheduling work, and optimizes resource allocation, contributing to improved project success. Our study provides valuable insights for both academic inquiry and industry practice, offering guidance on the successful implementation of AI technologies in construction projects. Our study's methodology, which combines quantitative analysis with established theoretical frameworks, enhances the credibility and applicability of the findings, particularly in the context of the construction sector. Overall, our study highlights the role of AI in improving project outcomes and offers practical implication for organization to optimize project success through AI adoption.

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